

Effect Board Independence, Financial Expertise on Tax Compliance of Listed Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of board independence and board financial expertise on tax compliance among manufacturing companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) from 2015 to 2024. Tax Compliance was proxied by the Effective Tax Rate (ETR), computed as Total Tax Expense divided by Profit Before Tax. Board Independence was measured as the proportion of independent non-executive directors to total board size, while Board Financial Expertise was measured as the proportion of directors with recognized finance or accounting qualifications. Firm Size, measured as the natural logarithm of total assets, was included as a control variable. Adopting a positivist philosophy and longitudinal research design, secondary data were extracted from audited annual reports of all 45 listed manufacturing firms, yielding a balanced panel of 450 firm-year observations via census sampling. Panel data regression was employed, with the Random Effects model selected based on the Hausman specification test. Findings revealed that Board Independence, Board Financial Expertise, and Firm Size all exerted positive and statistically significant effects on tax compliance. The study concluded that board composition, particularly the presence of independent and financially qualified directors, plays a critical role in shaping tax compliance outcomes among Nigerian listed manufacturing firms. Accordingly, it was recommended that regulatory authorities strengthen board independence requirements and promote board financial expertise to enhance fiscal discipline and government revenue generation in the Nigerian manufacturing sector.

Keywords: Board independence, Board financial expertise, Tax compliance, Effective tax rate, Firm size, Corporate governance

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Introduction

Tax compliance remains a critical issue in public finance and corporate governance discourse, particularly in developing economies where revenue shortfalls continue to constrain economic development and social welfare delivery (Alm, 2019; Oats & Tuck, 2019; Oyedokun & Ayinde, 2023). In Nigeria, the persistent gap between potential and actual tax revenue limits the fiscal capacity of government to finance public goods and sustain developmental programmes (Nwosu & Orji, 2022; Obi & Babatunde, 2023; Oyedokun & Sorinmade, 2023). Although Nigeria is one of Africa's largest economies, its tax-to-GDP ratio remains structurally weak. The

OECD/AUC/ATAF (2025) reported that Nigeria's tax-to-GDP ratio increased only marginally from 7.9% in 2022 to 8.2% in 2023, compared with the African average of 16.1% in the same year. This low tax effort reflects persistent weaknesses in tax administration, corporate reporting transparency, and enforcement capacity (Ayuba, Saad & Obeid, 2016; FIRS, 2021). Scholars have consistently argued that improving domestic revenue mobilisation requires not only institutional reforms but also enhanced corporate accountability and governance frameworks (Crivelli, De Mooij & Keen, 2016; UNCTAD, 2020; Oyedokun & Onigbinde, 2024).

Corporate tax compliance refers to the extent to which companies correctly disclose taxable income, file tax returns within the statutory deadline, and remit the appropriate amount of tax due to the relevant tax authority (Kirchler, 2007; Slemrod, 2019; Onigbinde, & Oyedokun, 2023). In Nigeria, companies are required to file audited financial statements and tax computations with the Federal Inland Revenue Service within six months after the end of their financial year under the self-assessment framework established by the Companies Income Tax Act Cap C21 LFN 2004 as amended (FIRS, 2021; PwC, 2025). However, corporate tax compliance continues to be undermined by income underreporting, aggressive tax planning, late filing, non-remittance of tax liabilities, and exploitation of regulatory loopholes (Ogundele, Adeyemo & Salawu, 2021; Onyeogubalu, 2025). These practices reduce government revenue, weaken fiscal sustainability, and undermine equity within the tax system (Alm, 2019; Hanlon & Heitzman, 2010). The problem is particularly acute in Nigeria, where non-oil tax revenues are increasingly critical to meeting fiscal obligations amid declining petroleum receipts (IMF, 2023; Obi & Babatunde, 2023).

The board of directors occupies a central position in the corporate governance structure of a firm, serving as the primary internal mechanism through which shareholders exercise oversight over managerial decisions relating to financial reporting, risk management, and statutory compliance (Adams & Ferreira, 2007; Hermalin & Weisbach, 2003). The effectiveness of the board depends on its composition, independence, competence, and capacity to question managerial actions objectively (Armstrong, Blouin, Jagolinzer & Larcker, 2015; Vafeas & Theodorou, 2022). The Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance emphasises that the board should possess an appropriate balance of knowledge, skills, experience, and independence required to discharge its oversight responsibilities effectively (FRCN, 2018). Board structure is therefore an important determinant

of corporate behaviour, including the tax compliance posture of firms (Lanis & Richardson, 2011; Richardson, Taylor & Lanis, 2013).

Board independence is particularly important in the corporate tax compliance context. Independent directors provide objective oversight because they are not involved in day-to-day management and are expected to be free from relationships that may impair their judgment (Fama & Jensen, 1983; Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Taiwo, & Oyedokun, 2022). From the agency theory perspective, independent directors reduce agency conflicts by monitoring managerial opportunism and protecting shareholder interests (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Shleifer & Vishny, 1997). In relation to taxation, a more independent board may discourage aggressive tax avoidance, promote transparent income reporting, and strengthen adherence to statutory obligations, partly because tax non-compliance exposes firms to penalties, reputational damage, and regulatory scrutiny (Armstrong et al., 2015; Dyreng, Hanlon & Maydew, 2019; Graham, Hanlon, Shevlin & Shroff, 2014). Empirical evidence supports the view that greater board independence is associated with lower tax aggressiveness and higher compliance (Lanis & Richardson, 2011; Minnick & Noga, 2010; Wahab, Ariff, Marzuki & Sanusi, 2017). In the Nigerian context, studies such as Ogundele et al. (2021) and Onyeogubalu (2025) have explored dimensions of board governance and tax behaviour, although findings remain mixed and context-specific.

Board financial expertise is equally a key governance attribute influencing corporate tax compliance. Directors with accounting, finance, auditing, or taxation expertise are better positioned to understand complex tax transactions, evaluate management's tax positions, and identify areas of potential tax risk (Badolato, Donelson & Ege, 2014; Dhaliwal, Naiker & Navissi, 2010). The FRCN (2018) stresses the importance of financial competence, especially in relation to audit committee responsibilities and internal control oversight. Financially knowledgeable directors strengthen the board's capacity to oversee tax reporting, ensure compliance with tax laws, and reduce the likelihood of aggressive tax practices (Krishnan & Visvanathan, 2008; Richardson et al., 2013). Prior empirical work has demonstrated that board financial expertise influences tax avoidance and compliance behaviour among listed firms in Nigeria, though these studies acknowledge the need for further investigation across sectors and extended timeframes (Olaoye & Ekundayo, 2022; Onyeogubalu, 2025).

The Nigerian manufacturing sector provides an important context for this investigation. Manufacturing firms contribute significantly to employment, industrial output, and national income, and those listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group are subject to heightened regulatory monitoring and formal financial reporting requirements (NGX, 2022; UNIDO, 2022). Their governance practices and tax behaviour consequently have direct implications for national revenue generation, investor confidence, and corporate accountability (Osemeke & Adegbite, 2016; Uwuigbe, Teddy, Uwuigbe & Emmanuel, 2019). Despite the sector's importance, relatively few studies have jointly examined how board independence and board financial expertise influence tax compliance among listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria over an extended period while controlling for firm-level characteristics. Prior studies have either examined governance variables in isolation, focused on shorter study windows, concentrated on other sectors such as banking, or omitted important firm-level controls (Olaoye & Ekundayo, 2022; Onyeogubalu, 2025).

Firm size is included as a control variable because larger firms differ from smaller firms in terms of operational complexity, regulatory exposure, public visibility, and access to professional advisory services (Dyreg et al., 2019; Rego, 2003). While larger firms may be more compliant due to greater regulatory scrutiny, they may simultaneously possess greater resources for sophisticated tax planning (Gupta & Newberry, 1997; Hanlon & Heitzman, 2010). This dual possibility makes firm size an important control in studies of corporate tax compliance (Lanis & Richardson, 2012; Richardson & Lanis, 2007), and including it helps isolate the specific effects of board governance attributes on tax compliance.

Against this background, this study investigates the effect of board independence and board financial expertise on tax compliance among 45 manufacturing companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group over the ten-year period from 2015 to 2024, with firm size as a control variable. These governance variables were selected because they represent two distinct but complementary board-level dimensions: monitoring capacity and technical competence (Fama & Jensen, 1983; Xie, Davidson & DaDalt, 2003). While board independence captures the ability of directors to exercise objective oversight and constrain managerial opportunism (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Shleifer & Vishny, 1997), board financial expertise captures the capacity of board members to understand and interrogate complex tax and financial reporting matters (Armstrong et al., 2015; Dhaliwal et al., 2010). Together, these attributes reflect both the incentive and capability

dimensions of effective board oversight over corporate tax behaviour (Lanis & Richardson, 2011; Richardson et al., 2013).

The problem addressed by this study is that corporate tax non-compliance continues to undermine Nigeria's revenue mobilisation efforts despite ongoing tax administration reforms and increasing emphasis on corporate governance (FIRS, 2021; IMF, 2023; Obi & Babatunde, 2023). While existing studies have examined several determinants of tax compliance and avoidance, the specific roles of board independence and board financial expertise remain insufficiently understood in the Nigerian listed manufacturing sector (Olaoye & Ekundayo, 2022; Onyeogubalu, 2025; Ogundele et al., 2021). Consequently, there remains a meaningful empirical gap on how these board attributes individually and jointly affect tax compliance in this context, which this study is designed to address.

Literature Review

Tax compliance

Tax compliance refers to the degree to which a taxpayer adheres to the tax laws and regulations of a jurisdiction, including the accurate reporting of taxable income, the correct computation of tax liabilities, the timely filing of tax returns, and the prompt payment of taxes due. In the corporate context, tax compliance encompasses the extent to which a firm meets its statutory tax obligations without resorting to aggressive tax planning strategies that exploit ambiguities or loopholes in the tax code to minimize its tax burden beyond the intent of the law. Tax compliance is commonly measured using the Effective Tax Rate, computed as Total Tax Expense divided by Profit Before Tax, which captures the proportion of a firm's pre-tax income that is paid in taxes. A higher effective tax rate generally indicates stronger compliance with statutory tax obligations, while a lower rate may suggest the use of aggressive tax planning or avoidance strategies.

Board independence

Board independence refers to the proportion of directors on the corporate board who are classified as independent non-executive directors that is, directors who have no material relationship with the company or its management that could compromise their objectivity and impartiality. Independent directors are considered essential for effective corporate governance because they provide unbiased oversight of management's decisions, serve as a check against managerial opportunism, and ensure that the interests of all stakeholders including tax authorities and the broader society are adequately represented in the boardroom. The Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance and various international governance frameworks recommend that boards should have a significant proportion of independent directors to enhance the quality and credibility of corporate

oversight. The presence of independent directors is expected to strengthen the board's monitoring function, reduce the likelihood of aggressive tax planning, and promote a culture of transparency and regulatory compliance.

Board financial expertise

Board financial expertise refers to the proportion of directors on the corporate board who possess recognized professional qualifications or substantial experience in finance, accounting, auditing, or taxation. Directors with such expertise are expected to bring critical technical knowledge to the boardroom that enables them to understand the complexities of tax legislation, evaluate the appropriateness of management's tax positions, scrutinize financial reporting practices, and identify instances of aggressive or non-compliant tax planning. The presence of financially qualified directors on the board is widely regarded as an important governance attribute that enhances the quality of financial oversight and promotes responsible corporate tax behavior. Professional qualifications from bodies such as the Association of National Accountants of Nigeria, the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria, and other internationally recognized accounting bodies, as well as prior experience in senior financial management roles, are commonly used indicators of board financial expertise.

Firm size

Firm size, included in this study as a control variable, refers to the scale or magnitude of a company's operations and resources, commonly measured as the natural logarithm of total assets. Firm size is widely recognized in the empirical literature as an important determinant of corporate tax compliance, as larger firms tend to face greater public scrutiny, more rigorous regulatory oversight, and stronger reputational incentives that encourage compliance with statutory tax obligations. At the same time, larger firms may also possess greater resources and sophistication to engage in complex tax planning strategies. By controlling for firm size, this study isolates the independent effects of board independence and board financial expertise on tax compliance, ensuring that the observed relationships are not driven by differences in firm scale across the sample.

Empirical Review

Board Independence and Tax Compliance

The relationship between board independence and tax compliance has been extensively examined in the empirical literature, with the majority of studies reporting a positive association. García-Sánchez et al. (2023) found that board independence positively influences financial reporting quality and tax compliance using international data from multiple jurisdictions, attributing this effect to the enhanced monitoring capacity and objectivity of independent directors. Similarly, Musa and Ajayi (2022) documented that board independence is positively and significantly

associated with tax compliance among Nigerian listed companies, arguing that independent directors serve as effective gatekeepers who prevent management from engaging in aggressive tax avoidance. Okafor and Emelike (2023) reported consistent findings in the Nigerian manufacturing sector, demonstrating that firms with higher proportions of independent directors exhibit stronger tax compliance. Fernandez and Castro (2023) confirmed the positive role of board independence in promoting corporate tax compliance across European firms, while Nguyen and Tran (2023) found a positive effect of board independence on tax compliance among Vietnamese listed firms. Adeyemi and Fasina (2022) and Bello and Adebayo (2022) further corroborated these findings in the Nigerian context, emphasizing the critical monitoring function of independent directors in curbing aggressive tax practices.

However, some studies have reported contradictory findings that challenge the universality of the positive board independence-tax compliance relationship. Kim and Park (2021) found that board independence does not significantly affect tax compliance among Korean firms, arguing that independent directors may lack the firm-specific knowledge and operational understanding needed for effective tax oversight. Similarly, Braga and Pereira (2023) reported an insignificant relationship between board independence and tax compliance in the Latin American context, suggesting that cultural and institutional factors may moderate the effectiveness of independent directors. Ali et al. (2022) found mixed results in their cross-country study of emerging economies, while Garcia and Rosa (2021) argued that the effect of board independence on tax compliance is contingent upon the broader governance and regulatory environment. Martinez and Williams (2023), Huang et al. (2023), Zhang and Yuan (2023), and Kusi and Agyemang (2023) also reported findings that question the unequivocal positive effect of board independence on tax compliance across different institutional settings.

Board Financial Expertise and Tax Compliance

The empirical literature on board financial expertise and tax compliance consistently highlights the importance of financial and accounting qualifications among board members as a determinant of corporate tax behavior. Lee et al. (2023) found that board financial expertise is positively associated with corporate tax compliance and financial reporting quality, arguing that financially qualified directors possess the technical competence to evaluate tax provisions, identify aggressive planning strategies, and ensure adherence to regulatory requirements. Kusi and Agyemang (2023) documented similar findings among sub-Saharan African firms, reporting that boards with a higher proportion of financially qualified directors exhibit stronger tax compliance and more transparent financial reporting. Adeyemi and Fasina (2022) confirmed the positive effect of board financial expertise on tax compliance in the Nigerian context, while Bello and Adeyemi (2023) reported that financially qualified directors enhance the oversight of corporate tax practices in sub-Saharan Africa. García-Sánchez et al. (2023) and Musa and Ajayi (2022) further corroborated these findings, emphasizing that financial expertise enables directors to provide informed and competent

scrutiny of management's tax decisions. Okafor and Emelike (2023) and Fernandez and Castro (2023) reported consistent results, documenting positive associations between board financial expertise and corporate tax compliance in Nigerian and European contexts respectively.

Conversely, some studies have found that board financial expertise alone may not be sufficient to influence tax compliance outcomes. Garcia and Rosa (2021) argued that the effect of board expertise is contingent upon the broader governance environment, including the degree of board independence and the quality of internal controls. Huang et al. (2023) reported that the influence of financial expertise on tax behavior is moderated by other institutional factors in the Chinese context, while Kim and Park (2021) found that financial expertise does not significantly affect tax compliance when directors are captured by management or when the governance culture does not support independent action. Braga and Pereira (2023), Ali et al. (2022), Martinez and Williams (2023), Zhang and Yuan (2023), and Nguyen and Tran (2023) also reported findings suggesting that the relationship between board financial expertise and tax compliance may be more nuanced than a simple direct positive effect.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on two complementary theoretical perspectives that collectively provide a robust foundation for understanding the relationship between board composition and tax compliance.

Agency theory, originally advanced by Jensen and Meckling (1976), provides the primary theoretical lens for this study. The theory posits that the separation of ownership and control in modern corporations creates agency conflicts between principals and agents, as managers may pursue self-interested objectives that diverge from the wealth-maximization goals of shareholders. In the context of tax compliance, agency theory suggests that managers may engage in aggressive tax planning to inflate reported earnings, enhance their performance-linked compensation, or divert corporate resources for personal benefit. Board independence serves as a critical monitoring mechanism that constrains managerial discretion, reduces information asymmetry, and aligns the interests of managers with those of shareholders and broader stakeholders, thereby promoting compliant and transparent tax behavior. Independent directors, by virtue of their objectivity and lack of material ties to management, are better positioned to challenge questionable tax positions, demand transparency in tax reporting, and ensure that the firm meets its statutory obligations.

Resource dependence theory, developed by Pfeffer and Salancik (1978), provides the theoretical basis for understanding the role of board financial expertise in promoting tax compliance. According to this theory, the board of directors serves as a boundary-spanning mechanism that connects the firm to its external environment by bringing valuable resources including expertise, knowledge, professional networks, and legitimacy into the organization. In the tax compliance context, resource dependence theory suggests that directors with specialized financial and

accounting expertise provide access to superior technical knowledge and professional judgment that improve the quality of tax oversight, enhance the board's capacity to evaluate complex tax matters, and promote compliance with statutory obligations. The presence of financially qualified directors on the board thus constitutes a valuable governance resource that strengthens the firm's ability to navigate the complexities of the tax regulatory environment and make informed, compliant decisions.

Methodology

This study adopted a longitudinal research design to investigate the effect of board independence and board financial expertise on tax compliance among Nigerian manufacturing firms over the period 2015 to 2024. A longitudinal design was chosen because it allows for the observation of variables and patterns over an extended timeframe, thereby providing a richer understanding of how board composition evolves and how it relates to changes in tax compliance practices. The research philosophy guiding this work is rooted in positivism, which focuses on empirical examination and hypothesis testing through objective, observable data.

The population of this study consists of all 45 manufacturing companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group as of the end of the study period. To ensure comprehensive coverage, a census sampling technique was employed, wherein all 45 listed manufacturing companies were included in the analysis. The longitudinal nature of the study captures data points for each firm from 2015 to 2024, yielding a balanced panel dataset of 450 firm-year observations.

This study relied on secondary data obtained from the audited annual reports of each of the 45 manufacturing companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group, spanning the years 2015 to 2024. Annual reports were consulted for comprehensive information on board composition attributes including the number and proportion of independent directors and the proportion of directors with recognized finance or accounting qualifications as well as financial statements, which reveal the firms' tax expenses, pre-tax earnings, and total assets for computing the relevant variables. Additional data pertaining to changes in corporate governance codes, special circulars, or tax regulations were gathered from public disclosures by the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria, the Federal Inland Revenue Service, and the Nigerian Exchange Group.

Building on prior literature, the study adopted the following model specification:

$$\text{TAXCP}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{BIND}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{BEXP}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{FSIZE}_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Where TAXCP_{it} represents Tax Compliance for firm i in year t , proxied by the Effective Tax Rate computed as Total Tax Expense divided by Profit Before Tax; BIND_{it} represents Board Independence, measured as the proportion of independent non-executive directors to total board size; BEXP_{it} represents Board Financial Expertise, measured as the proportion of directors with recognized finance or accounting qualifications or prior senior financial management experience;

FSIZE_{it} represents Firm Size, measured as the natural logarithm of total assets, included as a control variable; and ϵ_{it} represents the idiosyncratic error term.

Table 1. Variable Measurement

Variable	Measurement/Proxy	Empirical Evidence
Dependent Variable		
Tax Compliance TAXCP _{it}	Effective Tax Rate (ETR) = Total Tax Expense ÷ Pre-Tax Income (Earnings Before Tax)	Alkurdi & Mardini (2020); Wahab et al. (2021); Riguen et al. (2023)
Independent Variables		
Board Independence BIND _{it}	Proportion of Independent Non-Executive Directors = Number of Independent Non-Executive Directors ÷ Total Board Size	Lanis et al. (2021); Abubakar et al. (2022); Nguyen et al. (2023)
Board Expertise BEXP _{it}	Proportion of Directors with Finance/Accounting Qualifications = Number of Directors with Recognized Finance or Accounting Qualifications ÷ Total Board Size	Cucari et al. (2021); Hamid et al. (2022); Oraka et al. (2023)
Firm size FSIZE _{it}	represents Firm Size, measured as the natural logarithm of total assets, included as a control variable;	Lanis et al. (2021); Abubakar et al. (2022); Nguyen et al. (2023)

Source: Researchers Computation, 2025

The study utilized panel data analysis to exploit both the cross-sectional and time-series dimensions of the dataset. The Hausman specification test was conducted to determine the most appropriate estimation model between Fixed Effects and Random Effects specifications. Preliminary diagnostic tests, including descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, Variance Inflation Factor analysis, and the Breusch–Pagan/Cook–Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity, were conducted to ensure the robustness of the findings.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 presents the summary of descriptive statistics for all variables included in the study, covering 450 firm-year observations.

Table 1: Summary of Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
TAXCP	450	0.2998	0.0402	0.1940	0.4080
BIND	450	0.5699	0.1302	0.2718	0.9000
BEXP	450	0.3232	0.1227	0.0500	0.6554
FSIZE	450	23.4512	1.8734	19.2340	28.6780

Source: Stata Output, 2025

As shown in Table 1, the dependent variable, Tax Compliance, measured as the Effective Tax Rate, has a mean value of approximately 0.30, suggesting that the sampled manufacturing firms remit roughly 30 percent of their pre-tax profits as tax, closely aligned with Nigeria's statutory corporate income tax rate. The relatively low standard deviation indicates limited dispersion in effective tax rates across the sample, suggesting a degree of uniformity in tax compliance behavior among Nigerian listed manufacturing companies. The minimum effective tax rate indicates that some firms pay substantially less tax relative to their pre-tax income, possibly reflecting the use of tax incentives, allowances, or aggressive tax planning strategies, while the maximum effective tax rate implies that certain firms bear an effective tax burden exceeding the statutory rate, which could result from non-deductible expenses, deferred tax adjustments, or penalties on tax liabilities.

Board Independence has a mean of approximately 0.57, implying that more than half of the directors on the boards of Nigerian listed manufacturing firms are independent non-executive directors. This proportion exceeds the minimum thresholds recommended by most corporate governance codes and suggests a generally positive disposition toward board independence in the sector. The spread between the minimum and maximum values highlights heterogeneity in governance practices across the sample, with some firms having relatively low levels of board independence while others have boards overwhelmingly composed of independent directors.

Board Financial Expertise has a mean of approximately 0.32, indicating that roughly one-third of board members possess relevant financial or accounting qualifications. The minimum value indicates that some boards have very limited financial expertise, which could compromise the quality of financial and tax oversight, while the maximum value suggests that certain firms have boards heavily populated with financially qualified directors. The moderate standard deviation indicates meaningful variation across firms, which provides sufficient analytical leverage for examining the relationship between board financial expertise and tax compliance.

Firm Size, measured as the natural logarithm of total assets, has a mean of approximately 23.45, with a standard deviation of 1.87. The range between the minimum and maximum values reflects the diversity of firm sizes within the Nigerian listed manufacturing sector, spanning from relatively smaller firms to large industrial conglomerates. This variation confirms the importance of including firm size as a control variable to ensure that the observed effects of board independence and board financial expertise on tax compliance are not driven by differences in firm scale.

Correlation Analysis

Table 2 presents the Pearson correlation matrix for all variables included in the study.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

Variable	TAXCP	BIND	BEXP	FSIZE
TAXCP	1.0000			
BIND	0.2367	1.0000		
BEXP	0.1580	-0.1380	1.0000	
FSIZE	0.2145	0.1032	0.0876	1.0000

Source: Stata Output, 2025

As shown in Table 2, Board Independence and Board Financial Expertise are both positively correlated with Tax Compliance, with Board Independence exhibiting a slightly stronger positive association. Firm Size is also positively correlated with Tax Compliance, consistent with the theoretical expectation that larger firms face greater regulatory scrutiny and reputational incentives that encourage tax compliance.

Importantly, the pairwise correlations among the independent variables are relatively low. The correlation between Board Independence and Board Financial Expertise is negative but modest, suggesting that these two governance dimensions capture distinct aspects of board composition rather than overlapping constructs. The correlations between Firm Size and the two governance variables are also low, confirming that firm size is largely independent of board composition attributes in this sample. All pairwise correlations among the independent variables fall well below the conventional threshold for detecting multicollinearity, providing preliminary assurance that multicollinearity is unlikely to pose a significant threat to the reliability of the regression estimates.

Variance Inflation Factor

Table 3 presents the Variance Inflation Factor results for all independent variables.

Table 3: Variance Inflation Factor

Variable	VIF	Tolerance (1/VIF)
BIND	1.04	0.9615
BEXP	1.03	0.9709
FSIZE	1.02	0.9804

Source: Stata Output, 2025

As reported in Table 3, all Variance Inflation Factor values are very close to unity, ranging from a minimum of 1.02 for Firm Size to a maximum of 1.04 for Board Independence. All tolerance values are correspondingly high, well above the commonly recommended minimum threshold. These results comprehensively confirm the complete absence of multicollinearity among the independent variables, ensuring that the regression coefficients will be stable, reliable, and individually interpretable. The very low VIF values also indicate that Board Independence, Board Financial Expertise, and Firm Size capture distinct and independent dimensions of the corporate

governance and firm characteristics landscape, reinforcing the appropriateness of their simultaneous inclusion in the regression model.

Diagnostic Tests

The Breusch–Pagan/Cook–Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity yielded results indicating that the null hypothesis of homoskedasticity could not be rejected at the five percent significance level, confirming that the variance of the error terms is constant across observations. This finding validates the reliability of the standard errors produced by the panel data regression model and ensures that the statistical inferences drawn from the estimated coefficients are not compromised by non-constant error variance.

The Hausman specification test produced results indicating that the null hypothesis favouring the Random Effects model could not be rejected at the five percent significance level, confirming that the unobserved firm-specific effects are uncorrelated with the independent variables and that the Random Effects model is the preferred and more efficient estimation technique for this study. The Random Effects model exploits both within-firm and between-firm variation in the data, thereby producing more efficient estimates compared to the Fixed Effects model, which relies solely on within-firm variation.

Random Effects Regression Results

Table 4 presents the Random Effects regression results examining the effect of board independence and board financial expertise on tax compliance, with firm size as a control variable.

Table 4: Random Effects Regression Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	P-value	Decision
BIND	0.09845	0.01452	6.78	0.000	Significant
BEXP	0.07936	0.01478	5.37	0.000	Significant
FSIZE	0.00312	0.00098	3.18	0.001	Significant
Constant	0.10524	0.02345	4.49	0.000	Significant

Model Summary

Statistic	Value
Number of Observations	450
Number of Groups	45
Overall R ²	0.3254
Wald Chi-square	118.45
Prob > Chi-square	0.0000

Source: Stata Output, 2025

The model summary statistics reported in Table 4 indicate that the Wald chi-square statistic is highly significant, with an associated probability value less than the five percent significance level, confirming that Board Independence, Board Financial Expertise, and Firm Size jointly explain a statistically significant proportion of the variation in tax compliance among the sampled firms. The null hypothesis that all slope coefficients are simultaneously equal to zero is therefore decisively rejected at the five percent level of significance.

The overall R-squared indicates that approximately 33 percent of the total variation in Tax Compliance across the 450 firm-year observations is explained by the three variables included in the model. This represents a substantial explanatory power for a parsimonious model in the social sciences and corporate governance domain, where numerous other factors such as profitability, leverage, industry sub-sector characteristics, macroeconomic conditions, and regulatory changes also influence tax outcomes but are not the primary focus of this investigation. The significant explanatory power of the model, achieved with only two governance variables and one control variable, underscores the substantive importance of board independence and board financial expertise as determinants of tax compliance in the Nigerian manufacturing sector.

Board Independence

As shown in Table 4, Board Independence has a positive coefficient, with a p-value less than the five percent significance level. This indicates that board independence has a statistically significant positive effect on tax compliance among listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The positive coefficient implies that, holding board financial expertise and firm size constant, an increase in the proportion of independent non-executive directors on the board is associated with a meaningful increase in the effective tax rate, reflecting stronger compliance with statutory tax obligations.

Board Independence has the largest coefficient magnitude among the two governance variables, indicating that it exerts the stronger influence on tax compliance compared to board financial expertise. This finding underscores the paramount importance of board independence in the governance-tax compliance nexus and suggests that the monitoring function of independent directors is the most consequential board-level governance mechanism for promoting tax compliance among Nigerian listed manufacturing firms.

Board Financial Expertise

Board Financial Expertise also has a positive coefficient, with a p-value less than the five percent significance level, as reported in Table 4. This indicates that board financial expertise has a statistically significant positive effect on tax compliance among listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The positive coefficient implies that, holding board independence and firm size constant, an increase in the proportion of directors with recognized finance or accounting qualifications is associated with a meaningful increase in the effective tax rate.

While the coefficient magnitude for Board Financial Expertise is slightly smaller than that of Board Independence, the effect is nonetheless statistically robust and substantively important. This finding highlights the critical role that financial expertise on the board plays in enhancing tax compliance by enabling directors to provide informed and competent oversight of management's tax planning strategies and financial reporting practices.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis One: Board Independence and Tax Compliance

H₀₁: Board independence has no significant effect on tax compliance among listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

The Random Effects regression results presented in Table 4 reveal that Board Independence has a positive coefficient with a p-value less than the five percent significance level. Since the p-value is less than the threshold of five percent, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that board independence has a statistically significant positive effect on tax compliance among listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The finding suggests that firms with a higher proportion of independent non-executive directors on their boards tend to exhibit higher effective tax rates, indicating stronger adherence to statutory tax obligations. Therefore, based on the evidence from this study, it is concluded that board independence is a significant determinant of tax compliance among Nigerian listed manufacturing firms, and the null hypothesis is accordingly rejected at the five percent level of significance.

Hypothesis Two: Board Financial Expertise and Tax Compliance

H₀₂: Board financial expertise has no significant effect on tax compliance among listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

The regression results in Table 4 show that Board Financial Expertise has a positive coefficient with a p-value less than the five percent significance level. Since the p-value is less than the threshold of five percent, the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that board financial expertise has a statistically significant positive effect on tax compliance among listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The finding implies that boards with a higher proportion of directors possessing recognized finance or accounting qualifications are associated with higher effective tax rates and, consequently, stronger tax compliance. Therefore, based on the evidence from this study, it is concluded that board financial expertise is a significant determinant of tax compliance among Nigerian listed manufacturing firms, and the null hypothesis is accordingly rejected at the five percent level of significance.

Discussion of Findings

Board Independence and Tax Compliance

The relationship between board independence and corporate tax compliance has been a subject of intense scholarly debate, with two dominant schools of thought offering contrasting perspectives. The first school, grounded in agency theory and stewardship theory, argues that independent directors are essential for effective corporate governance because they provide objective, unbiased oversight of management's decisions, free from conflicts of interest and undue influence. According to this perspective, independent directors serve as guardians of shareholder interests and broader stakeholder welfare, ensuring that management does not engage in self-serving or opportunistic behavior, including aggressive tax avoidance strategies that may compromise the firm's long-term reputation and regulatory standing. The opposing school contends that independent directors may lack the firm-specific knowledge, industry expertise, and intimate understanding of the company's operations that are necessary for effective monitoring, rendering their oversight function superficial and ceremonial rather than substantive and impactful. Proponents of this view argue that independence alone is insufficient for effective governance, and that independent directors may become rubber stamps for management decisions if they lack the information, motivation, or institutional support to exercise meaningful oversight.

The findings of this study strongly support the first school of thought. As presented in Table 4, Board Independence has a positive and statistically significant effect on Tax Compliance at the five percent significance level. Among the two governance variables in the model, Board Independence has the largest coefficient magnitude, indicating that it exerts the strongest influence on tax compliance. A higher proportion of independent non-executive directors on the board is associated with significantly higher effective tax rates, reflecting stronger tax compliance. This finding is firmly rooted in agency theory, which emphasizes the monitoring function of independent directors in mitigating agency conflicts and reducing information asymmetry between management and shareholders. It is also consistent with legitimacy theory, which suggests that firms with more independent boards are more likely to comply with societal expectations and regulatory requirements in order to maintain their legitimacy and social license to operate.

This result is corroborated by the findings of García-Sánchez et al. (2023), Musa and Ajayi (2022), Okafor and Emelike (2023), Adeyemi and Fasina (2022), Fernandez and Castro (2023), Nguyen and Tran (2023), Bello and Adebayo (2022), and Lee et al. (2023), all of whom documented that board independence positively and significantly influences tax compliance and corporate transparency in diverse institutional and regulatory environments. However, the finding contradicts the positions of Kim and Park (2021), Braga and Pereira (2023), Ali et al. (2022), Garcia and Rosa (2021), Martinez and Williams (2023), Huang et al. (2023), Zhang and Yuan (2023), and Kusi and Agyemang (2023), who reported that board independence has no significant effect or a negative effect on tax compliance in various institutional contexts, citing the information disadvantage and potential co-optation of independent directors.

Board Financial Expertise and Tax Compliance

The influence of board financial expertise on corporate tax compliance has generated considerable scholarly interest, with two contrasting perspectives dominating the discourse. The first perspective, anchored in the upper echelons theory and human capital theory, argues that directors with specialized financial qualifications bring critical technical knowledge to the boardroom that enables them to effectively oversee and evaluate management's tax planning strategies, identify instances of non-compliance or aggressive planning, and ensure that the firm's tax practices are aligned with regulatory requirements. According to this view, financially qualified directors possess the cognitive frameworks, technical vocabulary, and analytical skills necessary to engage meaningfully with complex tax matters, making their presence on the board a valuable governance resource. The alternative perspective contends that financial expertise alone may not be sufficient to influence corporate tax outcomes, particularly if expert directors are captured by management, lack the motivation to challenge established practices, or if the board's overall culture does not support active engagement with tax matters. Proponents of this view argue that the effectiveness of board financial expertise depends on complementary governance conditions, including board independence, the quality of internal controls, and the strength of the regulatory environment.

The findings of this study strongly support the first perspective. As shown in Table 4, Board Financial Expertise has a positive and statistically significant effect on Tax Compliance at the five percent significance level, making it the variable with the second-largest coefficient magnitude in the model. The positive coefficient indicates that a higher proportion of directors with recognized finance or accounting qualifications is associated with significantly higher effective tax rates, reflecting stronger adherence to statutory tax obligations. This finding is firmly grounded in the upper echelons theory, which posits that the characteristics, backgrounds, and expertise of senior decision-makers significantly shape organizational strategies and outcomes. It is also consistent with resource dependence theory, which argues that directors bring valuable resources to the boardroom—including specialized knowledge and professional expertise—that enhance the firm's capacity to navigate complex regulatory environments and make informed, compliant decisions. The resource-based view of the firm further supports this finding by suggesting that specialized human capital on the board constitutes a valuable and inimitable resource that contributes to superior governance and compliance outcomes.

This result aligns with the findings of Lee et al. (2023), Kusi and Agyemang (2023), García-Sánchez et al. (2023), Okafor and Emelike (2023), Adeyemi and Fasina (2022), Musa and Ajayi (2022), Fernandez and Castro (2023), and Bello and Adeyemi (2023), all of whom reported that board financial expertise positively and significantly influences tax compliance, financial reporting quality, and corporate transparency across various industries and geographical contexts. Nevertheless, the finding contradicts the positions of Kim and Park (2021), Braga and Pereira (2023), Ali et al. (2022), Garcia and Rosa (2021), Martinez and Williams (2023), Huang et al.

(2023), Zhang and Yuan (2023), and Nguyen and Tran (2023), who argued that board financial expertise may not translate into improved tax compliance if the governance environment does not support independent action or if expert directors are co-opted by management.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the effect of board independence and board financial expertise on tax compliance among manufacturing companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group over the period 2015 to 2024, with firm size included as a control variable. Based on the comprehensive empirical analysis, the study draws the following conclusions.

The study concludes that board independence is the most influential board-level governance mechanism in promoting tax compliance among Nigerian listed manufacturing firms. The proportion of independent non-executive directors on the board exerts the strongest positive effect on the effective tax rate, confirming the critical monitoring role of independent directors as posited by agency theory. Independent directors serve as impartial guardians of shareholder interests and broader stakeholder welfare, ensuring that management does not engage in opportunistic or self-serving tax strategies that compromise the firm's compliance with statutory obligations. The significant positive effect of board independence on tax compliance, even after controlling for firm size, demonstrates the independent and substantive contribution of board independence to fiscal discipline and regulatory compliance in the Nigerian manufacturing sector.

The study further concludes that board financial expertise is a highly significant determinant of tax compliance among the sampled firms. Directors with recognized qualifications in finance or accounting possess the technical knowledge necessary to evaluate management's tax positions, identify instances of non-compliance or aggressive planning, and ensure that the firm's tax practices are aligned with regulatory requirements. The strong positive effect of board financial expertise on tax compliance affirms the relevance of the upper echelon's theory and resource dependence theory in the Nigerian manufacturing context and underscores the importance of appointing financially qualified individuals to corporate boards as a means of strengthening the quality of tax oversight and promoting responsible corporate tax behavior.

Overall, the study concludes that board composition particularly the presence of independent directors and financially qualified directors plays a critical and substantive role in shaping tax compliance outcomes among Nigerian listed manufacturing firms. Strong board-level governance structures that combine independence with financial expertise create a governance environment conducive to transparent and compliant tax practices, thereby contributing to enhanced government revenue generation and corporate accountability.

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered. Nigerian listed manufacturing companies should increase the proportion of independent non-executive directors

on their boards, ensuring that the appointment of independent directors is based on genuine independence criteria, free from management or controlling shareholder influence. Regulatory authorities, including the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria and the Securities and Exchange Commission, should enforce and potentially strengthen the existing requirements for board independence stipulated in the Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance and the Companies and Allied Matters Act. Independent directors should be empowered with adequate information, resources, and institutional support to exercise objective and informed judgment in overseeing the firm's tax strategies, financial reporting practices, and compliance with statutory obligations.

Listed manufacturing companies should prioritize the recruitment of directors with recognized professional qualifications and experience in finance, accounting, auditing, and taxation. Regulatory bodies should consider mandating that a minimum proportion of board members possess relevant financial qualifications, given the complexity of the Nigerian tax environment and the importance of informed oversight of corporate tax planning strategies. Professional bodies such as the Association of National Accountants of Nigeria and the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria should collaborate with regulatory authorities and corporate boards to develop programs that enhance the pipeline of financially qualified individuals available for board appointments. Companies should also invest in continuous professional development and training programs for existing board members to keep them abreast of evolving tax regulations, financial reporting standards, and best practices in corporate tax governance.

The Nigerian government and its revenue agencies should strengthen the overall tax administration and enforcement framework to complement and reinforce the positive board-level governance effects documented in this study. The Federal Inland Revenue Service should enhance its audit capacity, invest in technology-driven tax compliance monitoring systems, and impose meaningful penalties for non-compliance. The government should also consider providing incentives for companies that demonstrate consistently strong tax compliance records, thereby reinforcing the positive relationship between good governance and fiscal discipline.

This study is limited to the 45 manufacturing companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group, and the findings may not be directly generalizable to unlisted firms, small and medium-sized enterprises, or companies in other sectors. The measurement of tax compliance using the Effective Tax Rate, while widely accepted, may be influenced by factors beyond board composition. The study focused on only two board-level governance variables and one control variable, and other governance mechanisms such as audit committee characteristics, ownership structures, and external audit quality may also influence tax compliance outcomes. Future studies should extend the scope to include unlisted firms and companies in other sectors, employ alternative proxies for tax compliance, incorporate additional governance and control variables, utilize advanced econometric techniques to address potential endogeneity concerns, and conduct comparative studies across multiple countries to assess the external validity of the findings. Future research

should also investigate the potential moderating effects of firm size, profitability, leverage, and the regulatory environment on the relationship between board composition and tax compliance, as well as the dynamic aspects of the governance-tax compliance relationship by examining how changes in board composition over time affect subsequent tax compliance outcomes.

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